

HELIOS CA22119 COST Action Grant Period 1 (2023-2024) Report

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HELIOS Meetings

During Grant Period (GP) 1 (September 2023–September 2024), the HELIOS Action successfully organized three meetings: the first Working Group and Management Committee Meeting, as well as its inaugural Scientific Meeting.

➤ HELIOS First Working Groups and Management Committee Meeting

Dates: 15-16 April 2024

Location: Stratos Vassilikos Hotel, Athens, Greece

Participants: 53 (44 eligible for reimbursement)

Budget: € 54,125.00

Expenditure: € 36.602,90

Sponsors: AGIOS Pharmaceuticals (Gold), Lab Supplies (Silver)

Local Organizer: Dr Eleni Katsantoni, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens, Greece

Working Groups Meeting

The Working Group meetings spanned a day and a half, providing HELIOS members the opportunity to meet the action's leaders and familiarize themselves with the deliverables and milestones of each group and the overall action. Participants also had the chance to network with their peers, exchange ideas, and collaborate on defining the next steps for the action.

Management Committee Meeting

The second management committee spanned half a day on the 16th of April following the working group meetings in Athens. The members discussed the progress of the action, the core group delegated powers and decisions accordingly and planned the budget and upcoming activities for the rest of the year.

➤ HELIOS First Scientific Meeting

Dates: 03 October 2024

Location: County Hall, London, United Kingdom

Participants: 57 total, 25 HELIOS members (16 eligible for reimbursement)

Budget: € 25,600

Expenditure: € 17,049

Local Organizer: Dr Petros Kountouris (Action Chair), The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics

HELIOS organized its first scientific meeting, titled “HELIOS: Fostering Collaboration and Harmonisation in Haemoglobinopathy Research and Training through Synergistic Networking,” as part of the prestigious Annual Sickle Cell & Thalassemia (ASCAT) Conference. The meeting was a success, attracting participation from 22 ASCAT attendees together with the 25 HELIOS members who also attended the conference. Additionally, HELIOS was provided with a complimentary booth at the conference, allowing the network to be promoted to over 800 participants, many of whom expressed interest in joining the network.

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HELIOS Training schools and training opportunities

➤ Molecular research and diagnosis of hemoglobinopathies Training School

Dates: 17-19 April 2024

Location: Stratos Vassilikos Hotel, Athens, Greece

Participants: 33 (33 eligible for reimbursement), 11 Trainers

Budget: € 31,360 (€ 193 Daily allowance for trainers, € 175 Daily allowance trainees)

Expenditure: € 28.205,80

Sponsors: AGIOS Pharmaceuticals (Gold), Lab Supplies (Silver)

Local Organizer: Dr Eleni Katsantoni, Biomedical Research Foundation, Academy of Athens, Greece

The first HELIOS training school, titled “Molecular Research and Diagnosis of Hemoglobinopathies Training School,” was organized by Working Group 1 of the network. The school featured 11 hemoglobinopathy experts who served as trainers, delivering lectures on various topics such as genetic modifiers, variant curation, diagnostic standards and guidelines, and omics, among others. Feedback from the satisfaction survey showed that participants gained valuable new knowledge and established new connections. The majority indicated they would recommend future HELIOS trainings to their peers.

➤ (YRI) Monthly Discussion Club

Location: Microsoft Teams App

Participants: HELIOS members

Local Organizer: Dr Eleni Gavriilaki (HELIOS Young Researchers & Innovators coordinator), Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

The monthly Discussion Club, an online webinar hosted by Dr. Eleni Gavriilaki, HELIOS Young Researchers and Innovators (YRI) Coordinator, invites YRI members of the network to present their work, publications, projects, and ideas. This initiative is open to all members, encouraging active participation and contributions to the discussions. It needs to be noted that HELIOS STSM Grantees presented their work during the course of the club and disseminated their work funded by the action. To this date, the club has covered a diverse range of topics related to hemoglobinopathies, with great success and strong engagement from participants.

➤ Invited Speaker Series

Location: Microsoft Teams App

Participants: HELIOS members, Public

Local Organizer: Ms Stephanie Muth, StoryRelator Ltd., United Kingdom

The Invited Speaker Series is a new initiative organized by Ms. Stephanie Muth in collaboration with Mr. Fedele Bonifazi, the leader of Working Group 5. Each month, Ms. Stephanie conducts a broad review of the latest publications on hemoglobinopathies, identifying noteworthy, innovative, and intriguing research from authors around the world. The authors of these selected publications are then invited to present their work to the HELIOS network, sparking engaging discussions and fostering potential collaborations in the field.

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Grants

During the first grant period, the HELIOS COST Action awarded 11 grants to support knowledge development, promote young researchers, assist researchers from ITC countries, and enhance the dissemination of the network's work.

➤ Short-Term Scientific Missions (STSMs)

1. STSM Grant 1: Enhancing structural Haemoglobin variant annotation and data quality

Grantee: Ms Maria Xenophontos, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

STSM collaborating institution: Dr Celeste Bento, University Hospital Coimbra, Portugal

Grant amount: € 1,200

2. STSM Grant 2: Long-read-amplicon haplotyping for β -thalassaemia preimplantation genetic testing for couples with no additional family members.

Grantee: Antri Florentia Romanou, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

STSM collaborating institution: Dr Eftychia Dimitriadou, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgium

Grant amount: € 1,300

3. STSM Grant 3: Training for preimplantation genetic diagnosis of monogenic disorders, with emphasis on Haemoglobinopathies

Grantee: Dr Burak Durmaz, Ege University, Turkey

STSM collaborating institution: Prof. Jan Traeger Synodinos, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

Grant amount: € 1,500

4. STSM Grant 4: Geospatial modelling framework optimization for forecasting the global hemoglobinopathy burden

Grantee: Ms Mikaela Kontopoulou, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

STSM collaborating institution: Dr Edson Utazi, WorldPop Research Group in the University of Southampton, United Kingdom

Grant amount: € 1,500

➤ Virtual Mobility Grants (VMs)

1. VM Grant 1: REDCap configuration and implementation of HELIOS surveys

Grantee: Dr Kalia Orphanou, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

Grant amount: € 1,500

Topic: Dr. Kalia collaborated with the working group leaders to adapt the surveys for mapping hemoglobinopathy management across Europe and beyond using the REDCap platform. The Grantee streamlined and simplified the surveys to make them more user-friendly and implemented a system that invited participants based on their areas of expertise. Additionally, the system was configured to send automated reminders to participants who had not responded or only partially completed the surveys. Upon survey completion, Dr. Kalia assisted the leaders in exporting and analyzing the collected responses.

2. VM Grant 2: Harmonised guidelines for laboratory diagnosis of Haemoglobinopathies

Grantee: Ms Stefania Niki Minakaki, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

Grant amount: € 1,500

Topic: Under the guidance of Prof. Jan Traeger Synodinos, the WG1 leader, Ms. Stephania coordinated a comprehensive literature review focused on laboratory diagnosis guidelines for hemoglobinopathies. The Grantee organized the process, establishing a systematic approach for the literature search and the quality appraisal of the selected publications.

3. VM Grant 3: Organisation of speaker series

Grantee: Ms Stephanie Muth, StoryRelator Ltd, London, United Kingdom

Grant amount: € 1,500

Topic: In collaboration with Mr. Fedele Bonifazi, the WG5 leader, Ms. Stephanie has established an educational webinar series. Each month, she reviews the latest literature on hemoglobinopathies, selects the most interesting and innovative publications, and invites the leading authors to present their work to the HELIOS network and the broader public. The webinars are promoted via the HELIOS website and social media platforms to reach a wide audience. Additionally, the sessions are recorded and uploaded to the HELIOS YouTube channel, ensuring that anyone can access and follow the educational series.

➤ Inclusiveness Target Countries Grants (ITCs)

1. ITC Grant 1: Correction And Integrity of Duplex Base Editing for Fetal Haemoglobin Induction In B-Hemoglobinopathies

Grantee: Ms Nikoletta Papaioannou, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

Grant amount: € 1,500

2. ITC Grant 2: IthaPhen: an interactive database of Genotype-Phenotype data for Haemoglobinopathies

Grantee: Ms Anna Minaidou, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

Grant amount: € 1,500

3. ITC Grant 3: Risk Factors of Impaired Glucose Metabolism in Transfusion-Dependent Patients With B-Thalassemia: A Single-Center Retrospective Observational Study

Grantee: Ms Theodora Maria Venou, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece

Grant amount: € 1,500

➤ Dissemination Conference Grants (DCs)

1. DC Grant 1: HAEMOGLOBINOPATHIES IN EUROPEAN LIAISON OF MEDICINE AND SCIENCE (HELIOS) CA22119 COST ACTION

Grantee: Dr Sotiroula Chatzimatthaiou, The Cyprus Institute of Neurology & Genetics, Cyprus

Grant amount: € 1,250

M12 Milestones and Deliverables Progress

➤ Table 1-Milestones:

No	Milestone Title	Month	Status
1	Kick-off meeting completed, and management structure formed	1	Done
2	Action website released	3	Done
3	List of guidelines and protocols to be developed agreed among members	6	Done
4	Structure and schedule of the training programme agreed among members	6	Done
5	First release of dissemination and exploitation plan	6	Done
6	Public release of the harmonised and standardised CRF, with REDCap	12	In progress*

*Members of the HELIOS Network are actively involved in the creation, analysis, and finalization of two Case Report Forms (CRFs) from different initiatives, namely the INHERENT and ERN-EuroBloodNet networks. Once the analysis is completed and the CRFs are finalized, they will be adopted and endorsed by the HELIOS network

➤ Table 2-Deliverables:

No	Deliverable Title	M	Status
D1.1	Report on current diagnostic procedures in Europe and other participating countries	12	Survey done under analysis
D1.2	Harmonised guidelines for diagnosis, biobanking and variant interpretation for haemoglobinopathies	12	Systematic review and quality appraisal of existing guidelines done
D2.1	Standardised CRF for the collection of clinical and laboratory data related to haemoglobinopathies	12	In progress
D2.2	Harmonised guidelines for clinical management	12	Done-Endorsement of SCD guidelines from ERN- and EHA
D2.3	Report on current implementation of new and emerging therapies/treatments in haemoglobinopathies	12	Survey done under analysis
D4.1	Annual report on training activities of the Action	12	Done
D5.1	Action website	3	Done
D5.2	Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan	6	Done

D1.1: WG1 has developed and launched a survey to map current diagnostic procedures within the network. To date, the survey has received 31 responses from laboratories worldwide, and the responses are currently being analyzed. Once the analysis is complete, a report will be produced, and the results will be published in a scientific journal.

D1.2: WG1 has completed a horizon scan of the literature on diagnostic guidelines published in the past 10

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years. This search was conducted using a systematic approach, and the identified guidelines were appraised for quality using the AGREE tool. A report on the process has been produced by WG1. In the coming year, the group plans to develop either an expert opinion or a systematic review based on the literature and the diagnostic guidelines utilized within the network.

D2.1: See Table 1 for clarification.

D2.2: WG2 members have decided to endorse guidelines on Sickle Cell Disease recently published

D2.3: WG2 has developed and launched a survey to map current clinical practices within the network. To date, the survey has received 26 responses from laboratories worldwide, and the responses are currently being analyzed. Once the analysis is complete, a report will be produced, and the results are considered to be published in a scientific journal.

HELIOS Outreach

HELIOS, through the efforts of WG5 and Mr. Fedele Bonifazi, has developed and implemented a comprehensive plan to promote the network and its work. Key actions include:

1. **Website Launch:** The HELIOS website was launched within the project's 3-month deadline. It features dedicated sections for newsletters, webinars, events, news, and a blog to keep visitors informed about the network's activities.
2. **Science and Communication Plan:** A strategic Science and Communication plan was developed and initiated.
3. **Social Media Platforms:** HELIOS launched official social media accounts on Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn to increase visibility and engagement. The platforms are updated with regular posts and information regarding HELIOS and its activities, and general news regarding hemoglobinopathies to maintain and increase public engagement.
4. **Bi-Yearly Newsletters:** HELIOS introduced bi-annual newsletters to regularly update stakeholders on the network's progress.

Core Group Grant Period 1 Decisions

The HELIOS Core Group has actively supported the network's strategic decisions and the organization of its initiatives during the first grant period, holding monthly meetings to guide this process. In line with the delegated powers granted by the Management Committee (MC) after the first MC meeting, the Core Group made the following key decisions during GP1:

1. Reduced the daily allowance for trainees attending the "Molecular Research and Diagnosis of Hemoglobinopathies" Training School from €193 to €175 (also approved by the MC).
2. Approved the production, design, and costs of the HELIOS banner (€60).
3. Endorsed the Science Communication Plan developed by the WG5 Leader and Science Communication Coordinator (also approved by the MC).
4. Approved the production of promotional leaflets (€65) and pens (€160) for the HELIOS booth at the ASCAT Conference. Also, the increase in the LOS from €1000 to €2000 due to the increase in the number of participants in the ASCAT conference.

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5. Reviewed and approved the grant awarding process (11 grants were awarded during GP1), including support for publications, allocating €2,455.79 for the publication "Loss of Function Variants in SUPT5H as a Modifying Factor in Beta-Thalassemia" by HELIOS members.
6. Conducted a monthly review and approval of new HELIOS membership applications.

Grant Period 1 Expenses (01/09/2023-17/10/2024)

	BUDGET ACCORDING TO WORK BUDGET PLAN	EXPENDITURE
MEETINGS	66,111.77	53,651.90
TRAINING SCHOOLS	32,671.09	28,205.80
STSM GRANTS	10,000.00	5,500.00
VM GRANTS	6,500.00	4,000.00
ITC GRANTS	1,250.00	1,250.00
DC GRANTS	3,500.00	3,500.00
DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PRODUCTS	10,110.00	6,765.81
OTHER EXPENSES RELATED TO SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITIES	785.00	398.00
TOTAL	€ 130,927.86	€ 103,271.51